

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN THE PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE KOREAN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

M.D. Odilova

Trainee Lecturer, Department of Korean Language and Literature, Tashkent State Pedagogical
University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15594889>

Abstract. *In the context of globalization, the development of cultural competence has become a crucial aspect of the professional training of future foreign language teachers. This article defines cultural competence as an integrative personal quality essential for effective intercultural communication. The term "culture" and its significance in the context of foreign language education are explored. Special attention is given to the distinction between the concepts of "competence" and "competency," as well as to the role of classical literature in shaping cultural perception. It is emphasized that mastering a language is impossible without understanding the values, norms, and historical background of the respective culture.*

Keywords: *cultural competence, culture, competence, competency, globalization, integration, cultural perception, classical literature.*

INTRODUCTION.

The process of globalization has encompassed all spheres of human life, including culture. In the modern world, the histories of individual countries and peoples are interwoven into a single global narrative: events in one part of the world inevitably affect the lives of people in other regions. Globalization blurs the boundaries between national cultures, intensifying the mutual exchange of traditions, yet simultaneously poses the risk of eroding the uniqueness of individual cultures as their elements become integrated into the global cultural space. Under these circumstances, strengthening international cooperation and mutual understanding among nations becomes particularly important. One of the key means of achieving global harmony is the study of foreign languages—both on a global scale and in Uzbekistan, where interest in learning the Korean language and culture is steadily growing. However, practice shows that effective intercultural communication requires more than just knowledge of a foreign language; it demands a deep understanding of the norms, values, and traditions of its native speakers.

METHODOLOGY.

Historical experience and literary sources attest that genuine mutual understanding arises not merely at the level of words, but above all at the level of cultural values, symbols, and images deeply rooted in collective memory. True dialogue requires the ability to perceive the phenomena of another culture within the framework of its own value-based and semantic categories. This calls for the capacity to mentally “immerse oneself” in a different cultural reality—to become familiar with its historical experience, folklore, literature, and art—and thereby learn to think in the categories of that culture.

Turning to the terminological foundations, it is important to distinguish between the concepts of “competence” and “competency,” which are often used interchangeably in academic literature. As noted by A.P. Sadokhin, although these terms sound similar, they differ in origin and

meaning. The word *competency* derives from the Latin *competens*, meaning “appropriate” or “capable,” and refers to the internal qualities of a person and their ability to act effectively. In contrast, *competence* (*competentia*) traditionally denotes a defined range of powers and responsibilities formally assigned to an individual by regulatory acts. In other words, competence outlines the external boundaries of one’s duties and field of activity, while competency reflects the internal potential of the individual—their knowledge, skills, and personal attributes that enable them to perform their tasks effectively.

This perspective is further developed by M.Ya. Saraf, who emphasizes that *competence* reflects the “right” or the formal scope of duties to act within a certain field, whereas *competency* is a personal characteristic that defines one’s ability to achieve high results in that field.

Within the context of this study, particular attention is given to cultural competence as a specific aspect of professional competency, closely related to activity in the spheres of culture and intercultural communication. According to the scholars mentioned, cultural competence is understood not merely as a body of knowledge about culture, but as an integrative personal quality that combines knowledge, experience, and value-based attitudes necessary for effective interaction within a diverse sociocultural environment.

To gain a deep understanding of the concept of cultural competence, it is also essential to consider the fundamental ideas about culture itself. M.D. Guseinova traces the origins and essence of the cultural phenomenon, emphasizing that culture, as a specific form of human activity, emerged in the earliest stages of societal development. She notes that even in primitive communities, the foundations of cultural behavior and human interaction with the surrounding world were already being formed. Historically, the term *culture* had a practical meaning (from the Latin *colere* — “to cultivate the land” and the phrase *cultura agri* — “cultivation of the field”), but thanks to Marcus Tullius Cicero, it acquired a spiritual and moral dimension. Cicero introduced the concept of *cultura animi* — “cultivation of the soul,” linking culture to the development of intellect and morality. A similar idea in ancient Greek thought was *paideia*, an ideal of education and upbringing aimed at shaping the moral and intellectual qualities of the individual. These historical and philosophical foundations are important because they show that culture has been understood from the beginning not merely as a set of material skills, but as a process of spiritual development of the human being.

In the context of foreign language education, a significant contribution to the development of the concept of cultural competence was made by R.P. Milrud. He emphasizes that language and culture are inextricably linked, and therefore, culture must occupy a central place in language education. Milrud defines culture as a set of knowledge, behavioral models, and social relationships characteristic of both large and small groups of people. These elements are formed historically, passed down from generation to generation, and shape collective identity, allowing individuals to distinguish between “one’s own” and “others.” From this arises the dual role of culture: on the one hand, it serves an integrative function by uniting people through shared values; on the other hand, it has a protective function, safeguarding the community from dissolution within other cultural systems.

The development of cultural competence among future Korean language teachers requires not only a theoretical understanding of this concept but also a clear definition of the effective ways and methods to cultivate it within the educational process. This task can be successfully addressed by applying modern methodological approaches that ensure a holistic understanding of culture as both an educational value and a tool for fostering intercultural communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The methodological basis for professional training is built upon principles that integrate cultural knowledge, value orientations, and practical skills necessary for successful intercultural interaction. In this context, the following approaches are particularly significant:

Interdisciplinary Approach. The development of cultural competence involves drawing on knowledge from cultural studies, linguistics, sociology, psychology, and pedagogy (Zimnyaya, 2003). This approach fosters a comprehensive understanding of cultural phenomena and promotes a well-rounded perception of the target language culture among students.

Competence-Based Approach. According to Khutorskoy (2003), this approach focuses on developing not only knowledge systems but also the skills, abilities, and personal qualities necessary for professional activity in a multicultural environment.

Culturological Approach. Emphasizes the need for an in-depth study of the sociocultural realities of Korea through the analysis of literature, history, customs, and traditions. This approach helps students develop the ability to perceive cultural characteristics within their value context (Milrud, 2012).

Axiological Approach. Based on the formation of value orientations aimed at recognizing and respecting cultural diversity, this approach fosters tolerance, empathy, and openness towards other cultures (Sadokhin, 2007).

Practice-Oriented Approach. Involves actively engaging students in cultural and educational practices through participation in intercultural projects, cultural events, the analysis of literary works, and interactive activities. This enables the integration of theoretical knowledge with real-life experience in communication.

Reflective Approach. As noted by Levin (2006), this approach contributes to developing students' ability to engage in self-analysis and critically assess their own experiences of intercultural communication, which is essential for enhancing professional reflection and consciously shaping their pedagogical positions.

The comprehensive application of these methodological approaches creates the necessary conditions for effectively developing the cultural competence of future Korean language teachers. This not only prepares them for professional activity in the context of globalization but also fosters the development of a sustainable system of humanistic values aimed at promoting respect for the cultural diversity of the modern world.

CONCLUSION.

Thus, cultural competence constitutes an integral part of the professional training of a foreign language teacher, especially in today's context of active intercultural interaction. Its development requires not only linguistic knowledge but also a profound understanding of the culture, history, and value foundations of the target language community. Reflecting on cultural categories through literature, philosophy, and sociocultural practice enables future educators to build a more conscious and humanistic teaching approach—one that fosters not only effective learning but also respect for the diversity of world cultures.

REFERENCES

1. Садохин А. П. Межкультурная компетентность: понятие, структура, пути формирования //Журнал социологии и социальной антропологии. – 2007. – Т. 10. – №. 1. – С. 125-139.

2. Сараф М. Я. Формирование культурной компетенции как необходимое условие сохранения целостности культурного пространства и его креативного потенциала //Культура и образование: научно-информационный журнал вузов культуры и искусств. – 2017. – №. 2 (25). – С. 22-30.
3. Гусейнова М.Д. О ПОНЯТИИ «КУЛЬТУРА» В НАУЧНОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ // Международный журнал экспериментального образования. 2020. № 4. С. 13-17;
4. Мильруд Р. П. Обучение культуре и культура обучения языку //Вестник Тамбовского университета. Серия: Гуманитарные науки. – 2012. – №. 4. – С. 136-143.
5. Зимняя И.А. Ключевые компетенции как результат нового качества образования // Высшее образование сегодня. – 2003. – №5. – С. 34-42.
6. Хуторской А.В. Ключевые компетенции как компонент личностно-ориентированной парадигмы образования // Народное образование. – 2003. – №2. – С. 58-64.
7. Левин В.И. Рефлексивный подход в обучении: теория и практика // Педагогика. – 2006. – №4. – С. 45-52.